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Grain quality

Distribution of high density and low density grains in the panicle

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Increasing the number of high density grains (HDG) can increase yield potential of a variety. Varieties differ in the number of HDG per panicle. In a medium grain variety, most spikelets on the primary rachis branches are HDG and those on the secondary or tertiary rachis branches are low density grains (LDG). This study was conducted to find the distribution of HDG and LDG in relation to different grain sizes.

We collected 50 panicles at maturity from each of four varieties: BR11, BR25, BR5, and Tulsimala. From each panicle, grains on the primary rachis branches, secondary rachis branches, and tertiary rachis branches were hand-threshed and separated into HDG (specific gravity of

Distribution of filled grains in the panicles of varieties with different grain sizes.^a

^aGrain size: length × breadth (in mm) BR11 = 16.06, BR25 = 11.57, BR5 = 9.22, and Tulsimala = 8.14.

1.2 or more) and LDG (specific gravity of less than 1.2).

Most of the grain weight of panicles with coarse grain, (BR11), medium grain (BR25), and fine grain (BR5) was attributed to HDG. However, LDG mainly made up the panicle weight of a fine-grained variety (Tulsimala) (see figure). The spikelet numbers per panicle were 248 ± 10 for BR11, 270 ± 10 for BR25, 264 ± 10 for BR5, and 363 ± 10 for Tulsimala. Most of the LDG in Tulsimala appeared on secondary and tertiary rachis branches. The position of HDG and LDG probably depends on grain size and variety. Secondary and tertiary rachis branches contributed significantly to the panicle weight compared with primary rachis branches. ■

A simple, low-cost, on-farm technique for accelerated aging of rice

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Freshly harvested grain of all rice varieties exhibits poor cooking and organoleptic properties and cooks to a pasty, sticky mass. Aged rice is highly

preferred because of its excellent cooking and organoleptic characteristics. However, the natural aging process takes at least 3-4 mo and requires proper storage. We undertook this study to explore techniques for aging rice that could be practiced in households without much investment or technical competence.

IR50 and ADT36 rice samples harvested during late January 1993 were shade-dried and milled in a modern rice mill. From 100 kg of rice, IR50 yielded

60.2 kg head rice, 18.5 kg broken rice, and 21.3 kg bran and hull mixture, and ADT36 yielded 60.2 kg head rice, 18.2 kg broken rice, and 21.6 kg bran and hull mixture.

Sixteen-kg capacity metal tins were coated with blackboard paint on the outer surface and lids to enhance their heat absorption capacity (see figure). The tins were then filled with rice. Two small closed cups with perforated lids were filled with water and left in the rice at

Changes in the physicochemical, cooking, and organoleptic characteristics of rice varieties due to accelerated aging.

Variety	Aging period (d)	Cooked volume (ml)	Total soluble solids ² of gruel (g%)	Cooking time (min)	Volume expansion ratio	Length elongation ratio	Organoleptic scores ^b		Amylose ^a content (g%)	Amylase ^c activity (units)	Starch ^d (g%)
							Texture of cooked rice	Overall acceptability			
IR50	0	26.0	6.6	23.0	4.0	1.5	2.5	2.5	10.8	09.1	75.8
	6	29.0	5.5	26.0	4.8	1.6	3.0	3.0	12.6	21.8	73.9
	10	33.0	3.7	26.6	5.4	1.7	4.0	3.0	17.0	36.4	70.4
ADT36	0	25.0	6.5	23.0	4.1	1.5	2.0	3.0	10.1	10.9	70.0
	6	28.5	5.3	26.0	4.7	1.5	3.0	3.0	13.1	21.8	68.1
	10	33.0	3.7	27.0	5.4	1.7	4.0	4.0	17.8	36.4	64.5

¹g/100 g rice, ²Maximum score is 4, ³mg maltose produced during 15 min with 1% starch.